

ECONOMIC INTEGRATION AND ITS IMPACT ON THE
DEVELOPMENT OF THE COUNTRY'S ECONOMY, ON THE EXAMPLE OF
THE EUROPEAN UNION

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Annotation: *This article discusses the important role of economic integration in the development of the country, its positive impact on the economy. The role and necessity of economic integration in the development of the country is highlighted as an example of the European Union. The process of adopting the same currency among the European Union members and other key moments were highlighted in this article. In addition, the article discusses the stages of economic integration. Although, to illustrate the article, the extent to which the EU economy has changed through economic integration, the positive impact of integration on unemployment and the size of GDP, a key indicator of macroeconomics, has been confirmed by examples.*

Key words: *economic integration, EU (European Union),tariff and non-tariff barriers, single market, economic benefits, political benefits, unemployment rate, GDP*

Integration to the international economy is a course of actions among countries that typically includes the diminishment or disposal of exchange obstructions and the coordination of financial and fiscal approaches. Integration to the international economy points to diminish costs for both customers and producers and to extend exchange between the nations involved in the understanding.

Integration to the international economy is in some cases alluded to as territorial integration because it regularly happens among neighboring countries.

Regional Economic Integration can be defined as an agreement between groups of countries in a geographic region, to eliminate and finally remove tariff and non-tariff barriers to the free flow of goods, services, and factors of production between each other¹. The following are examples of Regional Economic Integration:

- **NAFTA** (North American Free Trade Agreement) An agreement among the U.S.A., Canada, and Mexico.

¹ <https://opentext.wsu.edu/cpim/chapter/2-4-regional-economic-integration/> Core Principles of International Marketing

- EU (European Union) A trade agreement with 15 European countries. APEC (Asian Pacific Economic Cooperation Forum) -This includes NAFTA members, Japan, and China.

We are going to focus our discussion of regional integration the international economy on the European Union. The European Community was formed in 1952. It has now become the framework for the present European Union. The European Union is a trade agreement between fifteen European countries. The Maastricht Treaty was signed in 1992. As the EU moves toward a closer economic union and a further expansion, they plan on instituting a single currency called the “Euro”. With the promise of consequently removing barriers and creating a free flow of goods between the European countries, the integration will create new opportunities and would show a substantial net gain from regional free trade agreements.

LEVELS OF ECONOMIC INTEGRATION

Following are the levels of integration from least to most integrated: Free Trade, Customs Union, Common Market, Economic Union, and Political Union. With free trade, all the barriers to the trade of goods and services among member countries are eliminated. In spite of this fact, each country can determine its own trade policies with regard to non- members. Members are free to determine the levels of protection applied to goods coming from the outside. Customs Union is one step closer to political and fiscal integration. This union also makes less trade barriers between the members of the union.

When territorial economies concur on integration, exchange boundaries drop and economic and political coordination increases. Specialists in this range characterize 7 stages of economic integration:

- a special exchanging range,
- a free exchange range,
- a traditions union,
- a common showcase,
- a financial union,
- an economic and total financial integration. ²

The final organize speaks to add up to harmonization of monetary approach and a complete monetary union.

Focal points of the Integration to the international economy the points of interest of financial integration drop into three categories: exchange benefits, employment, and political cooperation. More particularly, financial integration ordinarily leads to a lessening within the fetched of trade, improved accessibility of

² Levels of Economic Integration URL <https://transportgeography.org/contents/chapter7/globalization-international-trade/economic-integration-levels/>

merchandise and administrations and a more extensive determination of them, and picks up in effectiveness that lead to more noteworthy acquiring control.

The enormous positive impact of economic integration on the country's economy can be seen in the example of the European Union. The European Union is an organization system for the development of a joined together Europe. It was made after World War II to join together the nations of Europe financially. A populace of 370 million individuals speaks to the 15 part nations that share common arrangements that have brought an period of peace and thriving to Western Europe. These individuals pooled the coal and steel businesses to start the integration handle. In January of 1993, a single showcase where products, administrations, individuals and capital may move unreservedly was made with the foundation of the Economic Monetary Union (EMU). The EMU is based on two concepts: the coordination of financial approaches and the European System of Central Banks (ESCB) As of now, the European Union is moving towards Financial Integration with the creation of the Economic Monetary Union and the presentation of a single money, the Euro. No one can deny the economic and political achievements of the European Union through economic integration. The community, known as the European Integration Project, has moved away from a limited form of industry to an economic and monetary union. More precisely, this community agreement was radically different from the agreement of other regions. The theory of integration put forward by Bela Balassa set five shapes of economic integration. These are:

- free exchange zones, empowering unhindered trades and imports among members, but permitting them to have their possess assertions with non-participants;
- customs unions, which moreover permit free exchange inside, but force a common outside approach vis-à-vis non-participants;
- common markets, including flexibility of developments of components of generation and, depending on the nature of the more essential models, exchange in administrations;
- economics unions in which there are common rules and more broad coordination of national financial approaches; and total integration, including a single cash.

The economic core of the EU is the single market, characterised by the four freedoms of movement: of goods, services, labour and capital. Having evolved from a customs union, the single market – a wide-ranging 'project' initiated in the 1980s (European Commission 1985; Cockfield, 1994; Egan, 2001) – complemented the elimination of tariffs and quotas by curbing a plethora of non-tariff barriers.

But it also transferred powers from the national to the supranational level; as Michelle Egan puts it: 'to create a single market, the European Union has sought to limit the ability of its Member States to exercise regulatory sovereignty'.

The creation of the euro was, by any reasonable standard, a bold extension of the integration project. Plans for monetary integration in EU were under consideration from the 1960s, but only came to fruition right at the end of the 20th Century.

Share of European Union EU27 (from 2020) in the World Trade

Exports in million of ECU/ERO³

As we can see, the European Union is the second largest trade partner in the world. As a result we can see that economic integration has had a positive effect on the country's trade. Generally, the integration to the international economy typically leads to a decrease in the cost of trade, improved availability of goods and services and a wider selection of them, and gets in efficiency that leads to a greater purchasing power. Countries with the help of economic integration aims to reduce

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/> Share of EU in the world trade

costs for both consumers and producers as well as to increase trade between the countries involved in the agreement. Although, employment opportunities will be increased because trade liberalization leads to market expansion, technology sharing, and cross-border investment.

Employment rate (By age between 20 and 64)⁴

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/> Employment rate

Unemployment rate (By age between 20 and 64)⁵

These data show that the unemployment rate is not high in most EU countries. If we assume a natural unemployment rate of 5-6%, the unemployment rate in almost 16 countries of the European Union is stable. As it is known, the natural unemployment rate and GDP are closely related concepts. According to Okun's law, if the unemployment rate exceeds the natural unemployment rate by 1%, the country's GDP will decrease by 2%⁶. As much as economic integration has an impact on unemployment, it has an impact on GDP growth.

As a conclusion I would like to emphasize that, the European Union (EU) was created in 1993 and included 28 member countries in 2019. Since 2002, 19 of those nations have adopted the euro as one currency.⁷ According to the International Monetary Fund , the EU accounted for 16.04% of the world's GDP.⁸

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⁶ Okun's Law: Economic Growth and Unemployment <https://www.investopedia.com/articles/economics/12/okuns-law.asp>

⁷ European Central Bank Five Things You Need to Know About the Maastricht Treaty https://www.ecb.europa.eu/explainers/tell-me-more/html/25_years_maastricht.en.html

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